

Scrum VR: Virtual Reality Serious Video Game to Learn Scrum

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Abstract: Education is crucial for the growth of society, and the usage of effective learning methods is key to transmit knowledge to young students. Some initiatives present Virtual Reality technologies as a promising medium to provide active, effective, and innovative teaching. In turn, the use of this technology seems to be very attractive to students, making it possible to acquire knowledge through it. On the other hand, agile methodologies have taken an essential role within information technologies and they are key in Software Engineering education. This paper combines both areas and presents prior research about Virtual Reality experiences with educational purposes and introduces a VR serious video game that aims to promote the learning of agile methodologies in Software Engineering education, specifically the Scrum methodology. This application tries to bring students closer to their first days of work within a software development team that uses the Scrum methodology. Two evaluation processes performed with university teachers and students indicate that the developed video game meets the proposed objectives and looks promising.

Keywords: Virtual Reality; Education; Agile Metodologies; Scrum

1. Introduction

Agile methodologies are currently widely used in the software development industry and they have become extremely important in Software Engineering [1], and consequently in Software Engineering education. At the same time, Virtual Reality (VR) has started to be used in many sectors to train their professionals, allowing them to become familiar with their work environment and to improve their performance. For example, we can find applications that simulate medical operations [2], handle control panels in power plants [3], or perform psychological exposure therapies [4]. On the other hand, as Daniel [5] point out, these covid-19 times have forced education to largely adapting to an online format where digital material works best for students. At this point, it is possible to propose the use of VR as a key point for education.

The benefits of using educative VR applications include the promotion of skills development or knowledge acquisition as well as the enhancement of the learner motivation and the whole teaching-learning process. The first approaches of this technology applied to education have been studied for several years [6]. However, not all educative VR applications succeed in promoting the retention of the concepts presented to the user [7,8]. Consequently, it is important to focus the design of educational VR applications on fostering learning.

Keeping this in mind, this paper presents a VR serious game designed to teach trainees the key concepts of Agile software development methodologies, concretely Scrum. The game, named Scrum VR, aims to improve the teaching-learning process of the Scrum methodology by immersing the user into an experience addressing the key concepts of Scrum. Likewise, this application is proposed as an innovative way to motivate students to learn more about this type of methodologies. Scrum VR is intended to be integrated into future classrooms or online lessons with university students, but its

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40 usefulness is not restricted to the university environment. The serious game could also
41 be used by trainees who have just arrived at a company that adopts this methodology.

42 However, the development of an educational VR serious game is challenging and a
43 series of technical, artistic, and educational decisions need to be considered. In addition,
44 it is necessary to perform an evaluation of the developed application to ensure that
45 it is adequate and it would be useful in Software Engineering education. Therefore,
46 Scrum VR was evaluated through two independent experiments. The first experiment
47 was conducted by university teachers who are experts in agile methodologies. The
48 second was carried out by students who had recently taken the course that contained
49 the Scrum syllabus. Both experiments were carried out in order to guide and improve
50 the development of the game. The results show that Scrum VR is an innovative and
51 promising educational resource that may complement traditional masterclasses and
52 educational resources.

53 This manuscript describes the technical and artistic decisions made to achieve the
54 proposed objective through the following structure. Firstly, some examples of the use
55 of VR technology in education are analyzed. Secondly, the details of the design and
56 development of the tool are thoroughly described. Finally, the empirical evaluation of
57 the serious game is presented and the obtained results are discussed.

58 2. Related Work

59 The narrative capacity of the VR technology allows displaying the didactic contents
60 in a realistic way to the users, managing to develop valid lessons in this type of virtual
61 environments. In this way, modern examples of studies achieving greater user retention
62 using VR technology can be found. An example of this is the research conducted by
63 Ebert and Tutschek [9], which used immersive technologies to improve the effectiveness
64 and retention of the ability to perform medical fetal ultrasound, achieving a significant
65 improvement in user learning. Furthermore, some studies like the one made by Smith
66 *et al.* [10] indicate that the learning improvement achieved through educative VR ap-
67 plications seems to be especially significant in the initial phases of a learning process
68 when it is crucial to engage and motivate students. Accordingly, from the motivational
69 perspective, the use of educative VR applications seems to be highly recommendable at
70 the beginning of a learning process since it favors motivation and creates interest in the
71 learners.

72 Regarding this issue, prior research suggests an increase in motivation when teach-
73 ing using this technology, obtaining a consequent improvement in learning [11,12]. This
74 enhancement of motivation may be due, in part, to the fact that VR technologies are
75 generally perceived as appealing, especially to young people [11,12]. Furthermore, some
76 studies [7,8] found this type of virtual didactic experiences beneficial for student motiva-
77 tion, although they did not always affect significantly the knowledge acquisition with
78 respect to other traditional media. Consequently, it is important to focus the design of
79 educational VR applications on fostering proper learning in order to get benefits beyond
80 learner motivation.

81 There are far more initiatives bringing VR technology closer to the classroom
82 and examining its academic impact. For example, Liou and Chang [12] conducted a
83 study with 105 high-school students, achieving positive results in terms of knowledge
84 acquisition and motivation in scientific subjects. As an example, in higher education,
85 Tzong-Hann *et al.* [13] used VR technology to develop global collaborative project-based
86 courses, providing knowledge commonly taught in a theoretical way applied to practice.
87 Many more educative VR applications like these can be found in the recent survey
88 performed by Kamińska *et al.* [14].

89 Among the different educational virtual studies, it is worth highlighting those that
90 compare the suitability of VR technology versus other media formats. An interesting
91 example is a study by Raya *et al.* [15] who compared the motivation and learning of users
92 who experienced three-dimensional representations of pictorial art. This comparison

93 was made between different types of educational formats, including VR. As a result, an
94 increase in motivation was highlighted, although this visual representation did not stand
95 out in knowledge acquisition. In the comparison of different technological educational
96 formats, Moro *et al.* [16] conducted a study comparing VR, Augmented Reality, and
97 tablet-based. This study was conducted in relation to sciences and medical anatomy
98 and the results showed that extended realities have a higher level of immersion and
99 engagement in students.

100 Furthermore, some learning scenarios that require many resources, thus implying
101 high costs, can be simplified thanks to VR technology. Indeed, Román-Ibáñez *et al.* [17]
102 suggested that this kind of learning approach often reduces the cost of expensive prac-
103 tical lessons commonly presented in engineering education. That is why we can find
104 contributions [18,19] presenting complete teaching platforms using this technology for
105 different types of scientific subjects and provide a series of VR design ideas.

106 A low-cost approach to VR teaching is the use of mobile platforms for development.
107 Moro *et al.* [20] found no significant differences in learning in the use of mobile devices
108 using the same medical and health science education experience. However, they found
109 worse symptoms in relation to cybersickness with the use of mobile platforms. Never-
110 theless, the authors recommend the use of mobile platforms, although it is necessary to
111 pay special attention to virtual locomotion to avoid these symptoms.

112 There are long-standing guidelines that address these and other considerations,
113 thus facilitating the design of effective teachings through virtual environments [21].
114 In addition, Radianti *et al.* [22] recently conducted a systematic review to identify the
115 design elements and lessons learned in the development of VR applications for higher
116 education. Moreover, they proposed a research agenda recommending to increase
117 research on this type of teaching for its future inclusion in the classroom. However,
118 as technology evolves so quickly, new guidelines and recommendations are needed to
119 properly develop educative VR applications

120 On the other hand, focusing on Scrum learning, there are gamification initiatives
121 through classical games to achieve similar objectives to the one in this article. The
122 development of serious games to teach Scrum is of great didactic interest. For example,
123 Souza *et al.* [23] presented a board serious game to teach Scrum and they validated
124 achieving good results. A precedent to this project was the card game produced by
125 Fernandes *et al.* [24], which also resulted suitable for teaching Scrum. The results of these
126 studies show that Scrum seems a good topic to be taught through games, but will VR
127 video games be a good medium to learn Scrum?

128 The closest example found in the literature is the virtual experience presented in
129 2020 by Caserman *et al.* [25]. This experience uses modern VR devices to teach some
130 aspects of the Scrum methodology. However, the authors and their results pointed out
131 that the developed virtual experience should be more engaging. Our application, Scrum
132 VR, addresses this problem and differs from that application in several aspects:

- 133 1. Scrum VR is oriented to be used in academic environments and it can be applied in
134 real classrooms, rather than in professional contexts only.
- 135 2. Instead of using high-cost VR devices, Scrum VR uses mobile devices providing
136 greater access and availability.
- 137 3. Scrum VR is fully focused on making it attractive to promote the motivation of
138 students and engage them to the course. To achieve that the development and
139 validation processes were carried out in an intermingled and iterative manner.

140 3. VR Serious Game Development

141 Agile methodologies are currently widely used in the software development in-
142 dustry and they have become extremely important in Software Engineering [1], and
143 consequently in Software Engineering education. Many learning methods can be used to
144 teach this topic, including some involving gamification and serious games [26]. However,

145 to the knowledge of the authors, there are no VR applications aimed at teaching agile
146 methodologies and more specifically the Scrum methodology.

147 Scrum VR was carefully developed to impact both knowledge acquisition and
148 learner motivation. This VR serious game aims to improve the teaching-learning process
149 of the Scrum methodology by immersing the user into an experience that addresses
150 the key concepts of this methodology. This serious game can be useful for university
151 students who are learning Scrum as well as for apprentices who have just joined a
152 company using Scrum.

153 3.1. Design

154 A trainee could learn through the designed serious game about the key aspects of
155 Scrum: the roles that are usually involved in the development process (i.e., Scrum Master,
156 Product Owner, and developers), the meetings that are commonly conducted during a
157 sprint (i.e., Daily Meeting, Sprint Planning, Sprint Review, and Sprint Retrospective) as
158 well as some artifacts or techniques frequently used throughout a Scrum project such as
159 Kanban boards, Burndown charts, or Poker Planning [1].

160 The user, represented by the main character of the story, is a young worker who
161 has just joined a software company. He/she will learn about the target topics through
162 observation and interaction with the actors participating in a Scrum team, and espe-
163 cially through the Scrum Master (SM) character. The SM will tell the user about the
164 most important aspects of Scrum and will guide him/her through the processes of the
165 Scrum methodology. Furthermore, other characters such as the Product Owner and the
166 developers are also relevant during the experience because they will interact with the
167 user along these processes.

168 The whole experience is narrated linearly, and it is divided into four scenes with
169 an approximate duration of 8 minutes each. The following is a summary of the subjects
170 covered in each chapter of the developed VR serious game.

- 171 • Chapter 1: Scrum introduction
 - 172 – Agile and Scrum foundation.
 - 173 – Presentation of the Scrum Master and developers.
 - 174 – Operation of a Kanban board.
 - 175 – Software development life cycle.
- 176 • Chapter 2: Daily meeting
 - 177 – Conduction of a Daily Meeting.
 - 178 – Selection of User Stories based on their prioritization and estimation.
 - 179 – Usage of the Kanban board.
 - 180 – Usage of the Burndown Chart.
 - 181 – Usage of a dashboard involving quality metrics.
- 182 • Chapter 3: Sprint Review & Retrospective
 - 183 – Presentation of the Product Owner.
 - 184 – Conduction of the Sprint Review, including a Software product demo.
 - 185 – Conduction of the Sprint Retrospective, including an analysis of the Sprint
186 performance supported on the Burndown Chart.
- 187 • Chapter 4: Sprint planning
 - 188 – Definition of User Stories through dialogue between the Product Owner and
189 the developers.
 - 190 – Estimation of User Stories using the Poker Planning technique.
 - 191 – Prioritization of User Stories using the MSCW technique.

192 As presented, each scene addresses several learning objectives covering the main
193 Scrum concepts, so that by the end of the story the user will have learned about how
194 Scrum works. The scenes are described in detail below in order to introduce the narrative
195 and to explain some VR narrative resources that guide the user's attention: audio

196 explanations, visual support, character movements, object lighting, and interaction
197 through diegetic elements.

198 The story begins with the newcomer being welcomed into the hall by the SM,
199 who explains to him/her about the Agile principles and the Scrum framework. The
200 audio explanations are accompanied by some posters hung on the wall that support
201 them visually. The user's view (that is a first-person perspective) is guided through
202 the movements made by the SM and the lighting of the objects as depicted in Figure
203 1 (A). After the explanations, the SM offers the possibility to repeat them to reinforce
204 the concepts if necessary. When the foundation of Agile and Scrum is established, the
205 SM asks the user to enter the office to meet his/her colleagues, a question that can be
206 answered through an interactive diegetic button. Once inside the office, the developers
207 are introduced to the user. The majority are programming on their workstations, but
208 some of them are chatting and having coffee on the office couch (see Figure 1 (B)).
209 Following the presentation, the SM proceeds to explain the operation of the Kanban
210 board and the software development life cycle as shown in Figure 1 (C). The speech is
211 dynamized through interactions and curious facts (e.g., The SM asks the user if he/she
212 wants to know the origin of the word Kanban, which is Japanese and means something
213 like "card you can see"). Once again, the audio explanations are supported by visuals
214 and guided by the movements of the SM and object lighting.

215 In the second scene, the user is involved in a Daily Meeting which is being facilitated
216 by the SM. He/she discuss with his/her peers the next actions to be done by considering
217 the information provided by the Burndown chart and some quality metrics. The user
218 must select which user story to perform from the existing ones in the Sprint Backlog
219 based on their priority and estimation. This interaction is performed through diegetic
220 elements as depicted in Figure 1 (D).

221 The third scene is focused on Sprint Review & Retrospective. In this scene, the PO is
222 introduced and she takes a leading role. This scene is very dialogue-based and the user
223 has a high level of interaction thanks to many diegetic menus as shown in Figure 1 (E).
224 Moreover, the user participates in the demonstration of the software product increment
225 and the analysis of the Sprint supported on elements like the Burndown chart (see Figure
226 1 (F)).

227 Finally, during the fourth scene, the user attends a Sprint Planning, in which the
228 PO defines and prioritizes the user stories to be covered in the next sprint. The PO
229 explains to the user the MSCW estimation technique through audio explanations and
230 visual support as depicted in Figure 1 (G). Also, the user participates in the estimation of
231 these user stories through the Poker Planning technique. This involves high interaction
232 with other participating actors and the cards to be picked in order to estimate the story
233 points of a user story (see Figure 1 (H)).

234 3.2. *Technical decision making*

235 Beyond the educational design of the experience, there are several technical deci-
236 sions to be made in order for the serious game to be successful and meet the planned
237 objectives. Next, the most critical aspects are presented.

238 3.2.1. Platform and programming language

239 Scrum VR was developed for mobile devices with Android Operative System using
240 Unity 2019.4.13f1 game engine. Thus, almost everyone can easily install the application
241 on their own mobile and enjoy it just on a Cardboard, which is a very inexpensive
242 instrument. In this way, it is possible to bring the experience closer to a large number
243 of users. The choice of this engine was due to the fact that it is not complicated to
244 learn, using its C#-based scripting language, to create a low quality graphic appearance,
245 such as the one needed in mobile devices [27]. Its main competitor engine, Unreal, is
246 better for the development of applications with professional graphics, but with a higher
247 computational load, file weight, etc.

Figure 1. (A) The SM explaining the Agile manifesto. (B) The user meeting the developers. (C) The SM explaining the Kanban board. (D) The user selecting a user story based on its estimation and priority. (E) The user discussing a topic with the SM and the PO. (F) The SM explaining the Sprint performance through a Burndown chart. (G) The PO explaining the MSCW technique to prioritize user stories (H) The user participating in a Poker Planning.

248 3.2.2. Cybersickness and locomotion

249 In order for the virtual experience to be effective, it is critical to avoid or minimize
250 factors such as the feeling of cybersickness [28].

251 Firstly, as a high duration of an experience can lead to greater dizziness, it is im-
252 portant to shorten the times when possible and split the experience into chapters. For
253 example, the experience presented above was divided into four chapters of approxi-
254 mately 8 minutes.

255 Moreover, special attention has to be paid to the method of locomotion selected for
256 the entire virtual experience in order to avoid or minimize cybersickness. Specifically,
257 methods like the on-rails-guided locomotion [29] is highly recommended. This method
258 is of special interest when the experience is developed for mobile devices since it does
259 not require additional external hardware to interact with the virtual environment. In the
260 on-rails-guided locomotion, the user does not control the movements, being able only to
261 observe the environment that is shown to him/her during the experience.

262 According to the good practices in the methods of locomotion [30], the speed of
263 movement of the user should be always lower than a human walking during the whole
264 experience (less than 1.4 m/s). These displacements always follow a linear path, without
265 applying any kind of rotation to the user. In this way, the user is in charge of observing
266 where the action of the virtual experience occurs.

267 3.2.3. User interaction

268 The user interaction is critical to create a real application in which the user can
269 interact, going beyond a video in which the user just observes.

270 Since mobile platforms do not usually carry additional devices, the interaction
271 should be purely visual. The interactions should always be done with diegetic menus
272 that are fully visual and contained within the scene. Several examples can be found
273 in our serious game, like shown in Figure 1 (D, E, and H). These interactions can be
274 designed for different purposes, for example, to pick an element or to confirm the
275 understanding of a concept. The visual method uses a reticle visible to the user with
276 which he/she could select one of the options. To do so, the user should observe one of
277 them for some time, for example, 3 seconds. The progress of that action is displayed on
278 the reticle.

279 While the user's on-rails-guided locomotion could be done with a preset animation,
280 the interactions should be programmed to be reused during the whole experience. Since
281 all interactions usually follow the same mechanics described above, a simple interaction
282 was developed based on two main classes: Interactable classes, which can be activated
283 and are responsible for launching certain actions, and Selector classes, responsible for
284 activating the Interactable objects. In Unity, the scripts are associated with the elements
285 of the scene and, in this case, the activation of the Interactables can be done through a
286 RayCast generated from the point where the Selector script is associated. On the other
287 hand, the Interactable is in charge of measuring the time left to be activated and stores
288 what actions should be triggered when this happened. In this way, the effect of activating
289 elements with the sight was achieved. This process is explained through the sequence
290 diagram depicted in Figure 2.

291 3.3. Development phases

292 As mentioned before, the development of a proper educational VR serious game is
293 challenging. Therefore, the development of Scrum VR was divided into two phases and
294 it was closely linked with two evaluation processes.

295 During the first phase, the foundations of the project were laid. Educational deci-
296 sions were made by elaborating a first complete version of the complete script of the
297 experience. Technical decisions were also made regarding the development, technologies
298 and devices to be used, as well as the locomotion and interaction design. In addition,
299 artistic decisions were made by creating the working environment and acquiring the
300 character assets. With all these decisions taken, chapter 1 was produced. After that,
301 the first evaluation with teachers was performed to identify problems and gather ideas
302 potentially useful for the next chapters.

303 The second phase involves the development of the remaining three chapters. Some
304 modifications were made with respect to the initial plan thanks to the teachers' feedback.
305 Once the script was refined and the technologies and artistic elements were tested,
306 developing new chapters was easier. Indeed, it took approximately the same amount of
307 time to develop the first chapter as it took to develop the next three chapters. Once the
308 game was completed, a second evaluation with students was performed to check the
309 correctness of the application in educational, technical, and artistic terms. Some minor
310 modifications were made based on feedback from the students.

Figure 2. Secuence Diagram indicating the calls performed by the interaction system.

311 4. First Evaluation

312 This first phase focused on the first chapter to serve as a basis for developing the
 313 following chapters. The first chapter of the VR serious game was validated in technical
 314 and academic terms by Computer Science teachers. They tested the first chapter and
 315 evaluated it through an ad hoc questionnaire.

316 4.1. Evaluation instrument

317 The questionnaire included some initial questions about personal information (e.g.,
 318 age, gender, mobile device, VR experience, etc.) and a list of statements with which
 319 teachers needed to (dis)agree using a Likert scale from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally
 320 agree). The items of the questionnaire are presented together with the results.

321 4.2. Sample description

322 The demographic information about the 15 Computer Science teachers who tested
 323 and evaluated the serious game is as follows: they were 11 males and 4 females and the
 324 mean age was 38.92 with a standard deviation of 9.27. Furthermore, the 75% claimed to
 325 have a sound knowledge about agile methodologies and Scrum, but they had a disparate
 326 experience in the use of VR applications. Approximately 50% of the teachers had some
 327 or a lot of experience using VR applications, while the remaining 50% had never used
 328 this technology.

329 4.3. Results

330 In general terms, the users did not experience performance problems (the 100%
 331 declared that they did not suffer them), neither dizziness problems (the 25% got a
 332 little discomfort and nobody got dizzy). This allowed them to properly evaluate the
 333 serious game in technical and educational terms. Table 1 presents the quantitative

334 results obtained through the evaluation of teachers for each item, the mean (M) and the
335 Standard Deviation (SD) is showed.

Table 1: Quantitative results: Teacher's evaluation

Item	M	SD
Evaluation of Scrum VR		
My overall opinion is positive	4.17	0.94
The general narrative is adequate	4.67	0.89
The provided explanations are adequate	4.42	0.67
The artistic design is adequate	4.33	0.89
The objects shown (e.g., furniture, posters, blackboard, etc.) are adequate	4.25	0.97
The method of locomotion (i.e., how you move) is adequate	3.83	0.84
The accompanying sound is adequate	4.58	0.52
The stage lighting is adequate	4.75	0.45
The mechanisms of interaction are adequate	3.58	1.17
I have felt present in the experience (i.e., surrounded by the virtual world)	3.75	0.97
Potential academic impact of Scrum VR		
It can promote learning about Scrum	4.27	0.94
It can help to understand a Scrum professional context	4.17	0.72
It can be engaging and motivating for learners	4.5	0.52
It can help to energize the teaching-learning process	4.33	0.65
Evaluation of this type of VR applications		
My general opinion about this type of applications is positive	4.45	0.93
This type of applications are innovative	4.42	1.24
This type of applications are a good complement to traditional learning methodologies	4.5	1.0
I would like to use this type of applications with my students	4.08	1.38
It would be useful to incorporate more applications like this in the University	4.42	1.24

336 The overall opinion provided by the surveyed teachers about the educative VR
337 serious game is very positive and in general terms, they considered that the main
338 elements of the application (e.g., explanations, artistic design, interaction, etc.) are
339 adequate. Almost all questions related to the evaluation of the serious game are above 4
340 out of 5. The aspects valued slightly worse are those related to locomotion (3.83) and
341 interaction mechanisms (3.58), which are the most critical elements from the technical
342 perspective in this type of application. Anyhow, these results indicate that the experience
343 is correctly designed from the narrative and technical point of view and it would allow
344 the fulfillment of the educational objectives pursued.

345 Regarding the potential academic impact of the serious game, the teachers consid-
346 ered that it can promote learning about Scrum (4.27 out of 5) and help to understand a
347 Scrum professional context (4.17). Moreover, they thought that the serious game would
348 be engaging and motivating for learners (4.5) and it would help to energize the teaching-
349 learning process (4.33). These aspects are the key objectives of the serious game, which
350 aims to facilitate the knowledge acquisition of the learners, enhance learner motivation,
351 and enrich the teaching-learning processes.

352 On the other hand, the teacher's opinion about this type of educative VR experience
353 was also very positive (4.45 out of 5). The teachers found this type of application
354 innovative (4.42) and a good complement to traditional learning methods (4.5), so much
355 so that they were eager to incorporate them into their teaching (4.08) and some of them
356 requested the implementation of another educative VR serious game to support their
357 courses. In short, it seems that the use of VR for educational purposes has potential.

358 Finally, it is worth mentioning that the gathered comments were fully aligned
359 with the quantitative results presented above. Some of them are highlighted next: "The

360 *explanations are clear, the graphic recreation is pleasant and the narrative is sound*", "I think
361 *it is a very motivating learning resource and it will be greatly appreciated by the students*", "I
362 *loved it and I find it very useful, great work!*". Moreover, some useful suggestions related to
363 the locomotion and interaction mechanisms were gathered and they were considered in
364 the development of the following chapters.

365 5. Second evaluation

366 The complete VR serious game was tested by students from advanced courses who
367 already knew about agile methodologies as they had recently taken the course that
368 contained the Scrum syllabus. Once these students tested the game, they perform the
369 evaluation method defined below.

370 5.1. Evaluation instruments and techniques

371 To continue evaluating the serious game, two different evaluation methods have
372 been used. The first one was quantitative, while the second one was qualitative. Thus,
373 a mixed approach [31] was used in this evaluation as the quantitative data gathered
374 through a questionnaire was complemented by the opinions gathered through the focus
375 group method.

376 Firstly, a questionnaire similar to the one used by teachers was completed by the
377 students. However, as in this case, the students were testing the full game, new items
378 were added to the questionnaire. This questionnaire asks about personal information
379 and presents a list of statements with which students needed to (dis)agree using a Likert
380 scale from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree), questions to select an answer from
381 several options and open questions to gather comments about the aspects of the serious
382 game they liked the most and the least. The items of the questionnaire are presented
383 together with the results.

384 Secondly, several focus groups were conducted to collect qualitative data from
385 the students about the usage of the application in VR. The focus group method started
386 to be used in social sciences and currently it is widely applied in many domains [32],
387 including Software Engineering [33]. Focus groups are defined as a discussion involving
388 3 to 12 people and guided by a moderator who follows a predefined script to keep the
389 discussion focused [33]. In our case, three focus groups were carried out, and each
390 of them lasted approximately 25 minutes. The following topics were explored from a
391 qualitative perspective:

- 392 • **General appreciation.** What do you think about the application?
- 393 • **Knowledge.** What concepts about Scrum do you think are the most and least clear?
- 394 • **Usefulness.** How useful do you think it will be for the students who use it?
- 395 • **Improvement.** What aspects of the application do you think could be improved?
- 396 • **Striking features.** What aspects of the application have caught your attention the
397 most?

398 5.2. Sample description

399 The demographic information about the 12 students who tested and evaluated
400 the serious game is as follows: they were 10 males and 2 females and the mean age
401 was 21.00 with a standard deviation of 1.04. All of them were third-year students
402 enrolled in Computer Science degrees offered by the Politechnical University of Madrid,
403 Spain (ETSISI-UPM). The 83% were taking a Software Engineering degree and they
404 passed a course that teaches Scrum, while the remaining 17% were taking a Computer
405 Engineering degree and had no knowledge about Scrum. Regarding their background
406 in the use of VR applications, they had disparate experiences. Approximately the 60% of
407 the students had some experience using VR applications, while the remaining 40% had
408 never used this technology.

409 5.3. Questionnaire results

410 In this evaluation, the users also experienced no performance problems, neither
 411 dizziness problems (the 50% got a little discomfort and nobody got dizzy). This allowed
 412 them to properly evaluate the game in technical and educational terms. Table 2 presents
 413 the quantitative results obtained through the evaluation of students for each item, the
 414 mean (M) and the Standard Deviation (SD) is showed.

Table 2: Quantitative results: Student's evaluation

Item	M	SD
Evaluation of Scrum VR		
My overall opinion is positive	4.92	0.28
The general narrative is adequate	4.92	0.28
The provided explanations are adequate	4.67	0.49
The artistic design is adequate	4.75	0.45
The objects shown (e.g., furniture, posters, blackboard, etc.) are adequate	4.83	0.38
The method of locomotion (i.e., how you move) is adequate	4.25	0.75
The accompanying sound is adequate	4.75	0.62
The stage lighting is adequate	4.92	0.28
The mechanisms of interaction are adequate	4.83	0.38
I have felt present in the experience (i.e., surrounded by the virtual world)	4.92	0.28
Evaluation of key aspects of Scrum VR		
The explanations provided by the Scrum Master are adequate	4.92	0.28
The explanations provided by the Product Owner are adequate	4.83	0.38
The elements of the environment (posters, whiteboard, information monitors, pop-up explanatory cards) are adequate	5.00	0.00
The interactions or dialogues with other characters through menus are adequate	4.67	0.49
The choice of user stories on the Kanban board (chapter 2) is adequate	4.33	0.98
The estimation of user stories through Poker Planning technique (chapter 4) is adequate	4.83	0.38
Potential academic impact of Scrum VR		
It can promote learning about Scrum	4.83	0.38
It can help to understand a Scrum professional context	4.92	0.28
It can be engaging and motivating for learners	4.92	0.28
It can help to energize the teaching-learning process	4.83	0.38
Evaluation of this type of VR applications		
My general opinion about this type of applications is positive	4.92	0.28
This type of applications are innovative	5.00	0.00
This type of applications are a good complement to traditional learning methodologies	5.00	0.00
I would like to use this type of applications during my studies	4.92	0.28
It would be useful to incorporate more applications like this in the University	4.92	0.28

415 The overall opinion provided by the surveyed students about the educative VR
 416 serious game is very positive. It can be seen that students reported values above 4.25
 417 out of 5, and most of them are around 4.8 out of 5.

418 The students considered that the main elements of the application (e.g., explana-
 419 tions, artistic design, interaction, etc.) are adequate. Almost all questions related to
 420 the evaluation of the serious game were rated above 4.25 out of 5. The students also
 421 positively valued aspects related to locomotion (4.25) and, especially, the interaction
 422 mechanisms (4.83). Once again, the results reported in this evaluation indicated that the
 423 experience is correctly designed from the narrative and technical point of view and it
 424 would allow the fulfillment of the educational objectives pursued.

425 Similar responses can be observed in the group of questions related to the key
426 aspects covered by Scrum VR. The students rated all items above 4.33 out of 5. Further-
427 more, students were asked to select the part of the game they found most interesting.
428 The six key aspects of the serious game presented in the second section of Table 2 were
429 offered as options. Approximately the 60% of the students selected the estimation of
430 user stories through the PokerPlanning technique presented in chapter 4 as the most
431 interesting part of the serious game.

432 The highest scores were reported in the following groups of questions. Regarding
433 the potential academic impact of the serious game, the students rated every item of
434 this dimension above 4.80 out of 5. On the other hand, in the case of the evaluation of
435 this type of VR applications, they rated every item above 4.90 out of 5. Based on these
436 promising results, the use of this application in a real environment is of interest. Since it
437 could be easily accepted by students.

438 Finally, several comments were gathered from the students through the open ques-
439 tions posed in the questionnaire. Some of these comments emphasized the immersion
440 feeling, for example, *"It was great to feel like you are in a real company"*, *"The immersion helps*
441 *a lot with the introduction and familiarization with how Scrum works"* and *"The story is very*
442 *good, it's great to feel part of a real development case and to be able to participate in it"*. Many
443 comments remarked on the interaction possibilities of the serious game: *"I loved being*
444 *able to interact with the environment and that depending on the choice I made, the application*
445 *would have an appropriate response"* and *"I found very useful the discussion with the poker*
446 *game and how the others interacted with me depending on what I had done"*. Finally, other
447 comments like the following highlighted the educational purpose of the game, *"The*
448 *experience is very complete in general because it covers all important aspects of Scrum, I found*
449 *the explanations and interactions very accurate"*. Moreover, comments related to general
450 aspects about accessibility or usability were gathered and they were considered to refine
451 the serious game.

452 5.4. Focused groups results

453 The results of the focus group questions that were defined in the Section 5.1 will be
454 shown separately.

455 5.4.1. General appreciation

456 In overall terms, Scrum VR was very well received. No students indicated that they
457 disliked the game. Some general comments can be highlighted, such as *"The application*
458 *provide a vision of what a Scrum team will actually look like"* or *"It is super innovative and has*
459 *a lot of potentials"*. According with the presence produced by the VR experience, some
460 students explained *"I love the interaction with other characters and be able to make different*
461 *decisions"* and *"The experience is very realistic as if I was there"*. Many general opinions
462 were aligned with the feedback provided by the students through the questionnaire.

463 5.4.2. Knowledge

464 In terms of knowledge acquisition, the serious game was also very well valued.
465 Students who took the course expressed comments such as *"I have understood the topic*
466 *of estimation better through the application than during the course"* and *"The application is*
467 *incredible, it has summarized half of the course"*. Anyhow, some comments like this *"There*
468 *are other prioritization methods such as dot voting that are not explained"* highlighted that
469 the serious game did not cover all the knowledge acquired in the subject, which is
470 understandable as the length of the virtual experience is much shorter than a complete
471 course. On the other hand, other students said *"Until now I had not understood what scrum*
472 *was, but through the application, I think the main concepts are clear to me"*.

473 5.4.3. Usefulness

474 This aspect were also very positively valued in several ways. The students stated
475 that this type of educational material captures their attention and interest very well,
476 which is expressed in comments like *"It is very easy to maintain concentration with the*
477 *application, more than in most classes"* and *"The application can make you learn a lot in a very*
478 *short time and generate interest"*. Furthermore, the students indicated that *"Prior knowledge*
479 *was not necessary to understand what was being explained"*, indirectly expressing that the
480 game could be used at different times during the course (e.g., to introduce a specific
481 subject or to make a general review).

482 5.4.4. Improvement

483 There are some improvements pointed out by the students. Some of them were
484 implemented, but others did not due to duration or technology constraints. For example,
485 *"There is some knowledge about the Burndown chart that is not deeply explained"*, *"In terms of*
486 *accessibility, subtitles could be enabled"* or *"More visual metaphors could be added"*. As can be
487 seen, these opinions showed broad limitations due to technology.

488 5.4.5. Striking features

489 In general, the game has managed to impress students, but some features stand
490 out. All groups shared the same opinion and expressed through comments like this
491 *"The selection of user stories and, especially, the poker planning were my favorites parts of the*
492 *experience"*. Another group stated *"It's interesting to see how you make a mistake and feel bad*
493 *about it, as well as to appreciate how the team downplays it and you feel supported by them"*. In
494 a similar vein, another group indicated *"It was interesting to see someone developing in a*
495 *hurry and to see how it was detected that the code coverage was dropping"*.

496 6. Discussion

497 The evaluations performed with teachers and students report positive results and
498 suggest that the game will be well received by students and will be useful both in terms
499 of motivation and knowledge acquisition. It can be observed that while the ratings
500 obtained in the first evaluation are good, those in the second evaluation are excellent.
501 In that case, the users find the application extremely attractive, motivating and useful.
502 These differences are to be expected since the users of the second evaluation tested the
503 entire application and those of the first evaluation tested only one of the chapters. In
504 addition, it should be taken into account that the second evaluation was carried out by
505 young students, who tend to see the VR technology as more appealing. This strengthens
506 the idea that the experience is attractive enough to be applied in the classroom. In this
507 way, the difference with respect to Caserman's [25] work is fulfilled, finally achieving a
508 Scrum application that is attractive enough to its users.

509 The evaluations of Scrum VR indicate that this serious game is useful to convey
510 the general concepts about Scrum (i.e., roles, meetings, artifacts, techniques, etc.), as
511 well as certain details that show the spirit and values of agile methodologies (e.g., team
512 support, deadline and stress management, etc.). The interaction mechanisms and the
513 highly interactive parts of the game (e.g., selection of user stories, poker planning, etc.)
514 were very well valued by the users, who believe that certain concepts can be understood
515 in this way better than through traditional methods such as a teacher's explanation. This
516 was the main objective of the application as it was intended to go beyond an explanatory
517 video and create a really serious video game in which users have multiple possibilities
518 of interaction and learn concepts in an engaging way.

519 From the technical point of view, the teachers' evaluation was slightly lower in
520 terms of locomotion mechanisms. However, this was not reflected in the evaluation
521 made by the students. This may be due to the fact that the teachers tested only the first
522 chapter of the experience, as explained above. This chapter is the only one with user
523 locomotion, since it is necessary to take the user on a tour around the office. To avoid

524 this possible dizziness, the rest of the chapters do not contain any locomotion. This is
525 reflected in the students' evaluations. After the analysis of the state-of-the-art and as
526 mentioned above, the chosen locomotion method is the most appropriate according to
527 the needs of the project. This on-rails-guided locomotion method may cause a slight
528 sensation of motion sickness compared to other methods using more advanced VR
529 technologies [34]. However, those locomotion methods are not applicable to mobile
530 devices such as the used for this serious game [29].

531 Scrum VR can be used at various times with different objectives during a course
532 that addresses the traditional Scrum syllabus. Many usage strategies could be adopted:
533 the application can be used at the beginning of the course to introduce Scrum and
534 awaken the attention of the students, at the final part of the course to review the concepts
535 studied, chapter by chapter in different sessions to complement or reinforce the teacher's
536 explanations, etc.

537 7. Conclusions

538 The usage of VR in educational contexts is promising for many reasons. Prior
539 research shows a fair number of VR applications used at different educational levels (i.e.,
540 secondary education, higher education, and professional training) with very positive
541 results in terms of knowledge acquisition and/or learner motivation. The areas of
542 application are also varied and can be found VR applications designed to teach concepts
543 from several knowledge fields such as basic science, health, engineering, or arts.

544 However, to the authors' knowledge, none of the applications developed so far
545 addresses the learning of agile methodologies, and this is one of the novelties of this
546 contribution. Moreover, another distinctive feature of Scrum VR is that it was developed
547 for smartphones with Android Operative System, thus allowing the application to be
548 used by a large number of users. Moreover, technical recommendations regarding the
549 most critical aspects of VR video games such as cybersickness, presence, locomotion,
550 and interaction were considered to develop this application. On the other hand, the
551 programming architecture applied has proven to be useful for the generation of new
552 chapters. The architecture has proved to be versatile, being able to develop with relatively
553 low effort new interaction mechanics with the view, such as Poker planning or user story
554 selection.

555 The performed evaluations report very positive results and indicate that Scrum VR
556 would be very appreciated by students and would be useful both in terms of motivation
557 and knowledge acquisition. The video game seems to be highly suitable for the teaching-
558 learning process of Scrum because it facilitates the acquisition of general concepts
559 such as roles, meetings, artifacts, or techniques typically used in Scrum, as well as the
560 underlying values of agile methodologies. The evaluations here presented suggest that
561 the highly interactive parts of the game allow students to learn key techniques such as
562 the user to select user stories or to estimate them in a more effective way than by using
563 traditional learning methods. Thus, Scrum VR goes beyond an explanatory video to
564 transmit theoretical knowledge and it is a real serious video game to develop skills in an
565 immersive and interactive way.

566 On the other hand, although the results are mostly favorable, this application has
567 some limitations inherent to VR technologies. The most notable one is referring to the
568 cybersickness problem. Although locomotion techniques are used to minimize this
569 problem as presented above, it is very difficult to eliminate it completely. In the case
570 of Scrum VR, none of the users reported getting dizzy, but some did experience slight
571 discomfort.

572 Lastly, future work is presented. On the one hand, it involves conducting ran-
573 domized controlled trial studies to test the instructional effectiveness and motivational
574 impact of Scrum VR, as well as to compare different usage strategies of the application.
575 On the other hand, it involves developing new educative VR video games based on the
576 guidelines and the experience accumulated making Scrum VR. This kind of application

577 could be used in face-to-face and online modalities and they would be potentially use-
 578 ful for high school, university, or working students from many knowledge fields. As
 579 technology evolves, new modalities of human-computer interaction are included. In the
 580 future it would be possible to carry out studies that assess newer technologies as facial
 581 interaction or gesture recognition [35], evaluating their usefulness for education.

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 583

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